

Caste on Screen: A Study of Dalit Representations in Contemporary Indian Films

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***Abstract:** Films have always had a profound influence on society, just as society in turn, shapes the stories films choose to narrate. To approach cinema as a representational space is thus a challenge not only for filmmakers, who negotiate narrative and form, but also for audiences, who receive and interpret these images. The greater burden, however, falls upon scholars who attempt to critically engage with film texts, reading them through lenses rooted in the lived realities of social life. While Indian cinema has been widely examined for its socio-political dimensions, the specific and nuanced portrayal of Dalit characters continues to remain a striking absence. Dalits have historically been either absent, stereotyped, or silenced in Indian cinema. This paper argues that a bunch of 21st-century films, with all their limitations, mark a shift toward more visible and detailed representations of Dalit life, which complicate dominant cinematic narratives and open space for social critiques. The films chosen for analysis are Aarakshan (2011), Article 15 (2019), Fandry (2013, 14), Court (2014), and Geeli Puchhi (2021). The study examines how filmmakers portray Dalit experiences and the social realities they navigate, through the Dalit voices heard in these films. These film-texts portray multiple approaches, from direct*

engagement with caste-based violence and systemic discrimination, to subtle experiences of marginalization in urban settings.

Keywords: Dalit cinema, Contemporary Indian cinema, Dalit representation, Social films, Caste and cinema

Dialectics of Representation: Indian Cinema and Caste

Studies have highlighted how filmmakers like Shyam Benegal, Satyajit Ray, Deepa Mehta, and Anubhav Sinha employ social realism to foreground socio-political issues and marginalized communities in Indian cinema (Kushwah 6). Gehlawat (2024) examines how contemporary Bollywood films reflect and respond to socio-political shifts in India, particularly the rise of Hindutva, highlighting the influence of politics on film narratives and representations. While scholars have extensively analyzed the socio-political dimensions of Indian cinema, the precise and nuanced depiction of Dalit communities has remained a conspicuous omission. As Dhananjay Rai argues in his work *Contested Representation*, this absence is not coincidental but a systemic failure of the society as a whole, wherein cinema forms just one form of cultural production. Rai identifies three key challenges to the Dalit discourse in Indian cinema. First, the absence of significant studies in this area; second, the neglect of Dalit-specific angles in cinematic discourse which often creates a misleading homogeneity; and third, the lack of holistic analysis, leaving interpretations of Hindi cinema incomplete and detached from the Dalit experience. This paper aims to address this gap in existing film discourses. In contemporary India, authentic Dalit representation in cinema has become vital for social commentary and change, challenging dominant narratives and highlighting ongoing caste discrimination. This study provides a preliminary

overview of 21st-century films depicting Dalit experiences, focusing on two key questions: how Dalits are portrayed in Indian films, and what these portrayals reveal about identity, representation, resistance, and aspiration of Dalits in contemporary society.

In order to truly understand cinematic shifts around portrayal of Dalit characters in films, it is necessary to move beyond a simple measure of *realism* in cinematic depictions. Therefore, this article also foregrounds some ground paradoxes – 1) How does an art form like cinema, which is inherently shaped by dramatic conventions, aesthetic choices, and commercial interests, depict a social reality as complex and painful as caste?; 2) The representation of a tragedy on screen, for instance, is not a neutral act; it is mediated by the filmmaker's choices on tone, genre, aesthetic, and commercial purposes; 3) Films with social commentaries, particularly within a commercial industry like Bollywood, are often subject to market forces and the pressures of profitability, which can influence their narrative choices, messaging, and overall political stance. Thus, how far can films be selected as a space to understand societal representations?; and, lastly, how these aesthetic and commercial pressures are either subverted or reproduced in those films that claim to represent the Dalit experience.

The representation of caste is not simply a matter of depicting an accurate reality; it is also about the choices filmmakers make in genre, narrative, and characterization. This study undertakes a critical analysis of five key film texts from the 21st century to understand the evolving cinematic interpretations of Dalit life and the reception of these portrayals. The films chosen represent distinct approaches to the focus of this study. Prakash Jha's *Aarakshan* (2011) directly engages with the contested issue

of caste-based reservation and quota-system in educational institutions. Anubhav Sinha's *Article 15* (2019) follows an honest police officer's investigation into a heinous crime, serving as a mainstream uncovering of entrenched caste-based violence. The Marathi film *Fandry* (2013), directed by Nagraj Manjule, offers a visceral narrative of a Dalit boy's struggle against everyday caste discrimination and untouchability. Chaitanya Tamhane's *Court* (2014) uses a detached, observational style to expose the absurdity and systemic bias of India's legal system, highlighting its dehumanizing impact on a folk singer from an oppressed community. Finally, Neeraj Ghaywan's film segment *Geeli Puchhi* (2021) from the cinematic anthology *Ajeeb Daastaans* explores the subtle and insidious nature of caste discrimination in a modern, urban workplace through the lens of a complicated friendship. By examining these diverse cinematic approaches, in the sequence of the progress of Dalit characterization in the mentioned films, this paper will explore how emerging Indian cinema is both creating and challenging the social language used to represent the Dalit community.

Analysis of Film-texts: Cas(t)e Studies

Aarakshan

The film *Aarakshan* (2011) serves as a focal point for examining how caste and reservation policies are depicted in contemporary Hindi cinema. The movie sparked significant public debate and controversy, reflecting the deep-rooted tensions and evolving narratives around caste-based affirmative action in India. Shanker (2023) observes that recent Dalit representations in films such as *Aarakshan* and *Masaan* move beyond narratives of victimhood, portraying Dalit characters with agency, aspirations, and resilience. She argues that such films attempt to humanize Dalit experiences,

unlike earlier cinematic attempts exemplified by the Bachchan era, foregrounding issues of education, social mobility, and individual growth, while simultaneously serving as broad social commentaries on caste-based discriminations. Studies have confirmed how strongly the film's release ignited protests and controversy, especially among opponents of reservation policies across the country. The film's framing of education as the primary tool for Dalit upliftment not only resonates with Ambedkar's vision, but also highlights what Bourdieu calls the uneven distribution of cultural and institutional capital, where degrees and credentials alone cannot aid to erase hierarchical oppression. Similar tension regarding SC/ST reservations is underscored by Yashica Dutt's 2019 memoir *Coming Out as Dalit*, where she shows how even second/third-generation Dalits who are educated and professionally successful must still *pass* or hide their caste to avoid stigma (akin to the phenomenon of racial *passing* in white-dominated worlds). The case of IAS officer Tina Dabi, also noted by Dutt, illustrates the paradox that despite topping one of the most competitive central exams, her Dalit identity became the center of public discourse, revealing that structural prejudice persists beyond individual merit. Situating *Aarakshan* into discourses around reservation for Scheduled Castes in India, leads one to a bigger question, i.e., whether education and reservation alone can undo entrenched caste privilege without deeper social transformation?

While *Aarakshan* makes a rare mainstream engagement with reservation policies, its flimsy representation of Dalits also reproduces some familiar power dynamics. The film gives us an upper-caste hero, Dr. Prabhakar Anand (played by Amitabh Bachchan, who also played similar *savior-hero* roles in films like *Zanjeer*). Dr. Anand's *saviour complex* shifts focus from Dalit agency to upper-caste moral excellence. At the same time, the

movie frames caste struggle largely in educational and economic spaces. Caste does not appear only as spatial or ritual exclusion in the film (as in older literature centering Dalits like Mulk Raj Anand's *Untouchable*) but as competition for jobs, college seats, and upward mobility, thereby portraying a significant shift in Dalit representation. The policy of reservation becomes the fulcrum around which moral integrity, institutional corruption, and individual success revolve. The resolution suggests that Dalit liberation is achievable via individual merit and access to quality education, ideas closely aligned with Ambedkarite thought, and as Nelson Mandela also emphasized education as "the most powerful weapon" that can change the world. The film's support for affirmative action in higher education brought long-standing debates about caste-based *quotas* back into the national spotlight, catalyzing the ongoing tension between advocates and critics of affirmative policies.

Article 15

Film *Article 15* (2019), portrays an urban-educated police officer who arrives in a rural village and investigates the disappearance of two Dalit girls, quickly discovering that the crime and its subsequent cover-up are rooted in brutal, entrenched caste-based discrimination perpetrated by the dominant class and shielded by corrupt local law enforcement. Interestingly, the film's title itself is a commentary on the Indian Constitution's "Article 15" that strictly prohibits any form of caste discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth (Article 15, Law and Policy Research Trust). The film's title is a reminder of the huge gap existing between constitutional reforms (in theory) and their real life explorations (in practice).

Ayan Ranjan (played by Ayushmann Khurrana), a Superintendent of Police who happens to come from an upper-caste urban background, sees caste oppression in the village as shocking and surprising, a framing that risks making the everyday reality of caste seem exceptional. In reality, discrimination often exists silently, under the surface, shaping lives in subtle but persistent ways. Yet, by presenting the story through this lens, the film reaches upper-caste audiences effectively, educating them about systemic oppression and the role each individual plays in sustaining it. As Galtung notes in his Peace Studies frameworks, that although Indian religious traditions emphasize inner peace (*shanti*) and goodwill (*sadbhavana*), on ground, caste hierarchies seem to disrupt such ideals, revealing the gap between ethical philosophy and social reality (22–25), a humorous irony also reflected in films like *Article 15*. Foucault's power frameworks also explain the film's depictions of institutional bias and social hierarchies, while leaving room for more nuanced Dalit portrayals in future cinematic work. Academic discussions have also underscored the film's strengths in raising awareness of social issues, while also critiquing its narrative strategies and alignment with state power. Althusserian frameworks also corroborate the significance of both ideological and repressive state apparatuses of the state that need intervention to understand and improve its deep rooted caste-problem.

Fandry

In *Fandry* (2013, 2014), directed by Nagraj Manjule, the film follows Jabya, a young Dalit boy in rural Maharashtra, who struggles not only against everyday caste discrimination but also with the pain of unrequited love for Shalu, an upper-caste girl. The central issue is how caste structures dictate personal relationships. Love, desire, and marriage are all constrained by rigid social

hierarchies. As Yogesh Maitreya observes, “caste is the warden of love” (Maitreya, *Water in a Broken Pot*, 72), a reality poignantly reflected in Jabya’s experiences. *Fandry* powerfully depicts caste humiliation through language and symbolism. Jabya and his family are demeaned as *darkie*, *scum*, and *dirty pig*, illustrating how caste violence is embedded in everyday speech. Jabya’s refusal to remove a piglet, contrasted with his father’s compliance, hints at how education enables resistance to hereditary labour expectations. A pivotal scene involves the removal of a piglet from a pit, which Jabya refuses to do. This denial, an act his father Kachrya cannot himself perform, illustrates how education empowers the younger generation to resist caste-based labour expectations. Jabya’s refusal marks a significant departure from the inherited submission that binds his father, who, due to illiteracy and dependence, remains unable to challenge caste hierarchies. The reaction of Patil, a high-caste villager to Jabya’s dismissal, underscores such dynamic –

Patil: Your son is getting too big for his boots. He talked back to me. He isn’t like you.

Kachrya: Disgraceful! (*Fandry*, subtitles)

The phrase “too big for his boots” encapsulates upper-caste anxiety over Dalit assertion. Patil’s words imply that equality is intolerable when it threatens caste hierarchies. His anxious reaction implies that Dalits must *know their place* and remain submissive.

The title of the film seems inspired by the politics of the pig, which is both despised by upper castes and consumed by not only Dalits but also many upper caste Hindus. Hence, *fandry* becomes a culinary metaphor for the hypocrisy of purity-pollution narratives within untouchability discourses. Yogesh Maitreya informs that “*Fandry*, meaning ‘pig’ in the dialect spoken by *Kaikadi* (untouchable) community, is the central symbol of stigma

of untouchability in *Fandry*” (rti_admin). Interestingly, in Jabya’s father Kachrya’s plea, “I don’t want to be an outcast!” (*Fandry*), Manjule’s film also reveals the irony of internalized fear to *become* an outcast while already *existing* as an outcast.

However, films like *Fandry*, which bring real Dalit characters to the screen, work as pioneering role models for Dalit youths, not only by showing them how to survive humiliation but also illustrating how to resist it. Yogesh Maitreya, reflecting on the power of such films that rightfully depict Dalit lives, writes –

Yes, Jabya tells us how to live now. That’s how history is being made and the shackles of slavery are being broken down. That is how people from the hamlets, like my grandfather, fought against the casteist forces, acting as rebels and created new life for themselves. That’s how my father toiled hard to make us study. Yes, that’s how we learn to give a tight slap to the established system of caste...Yes, we got our new hero in JABYA. (rti_admin)

The final image of Jabya throwing a stone at the screen symbolically captures the psychological impulse of the long-oppressed Dalit community to resist, thereby reflecting the idea that sustained oppression inevitably provokes a confrontation with injustice.

Court

Courtroom films are a popular genre that blends dramatic storytelling with legal-ethical dilemmas, often reflecting broader societal issues. These films range from fictional dramas to documentaries and biopics, exploring the tension between law, justice, and truth. In *Court* (2014), directed by Chaitanya

Tamhane, we see portrayal of the slow, bureaucratic trial of Narayan Kamble, an aging Dalit folk singer accused of abetting a young woman's suicide. The central issue is the systemic invisibility and dehumanization of marginalized communities within India's legal and institutional structures. Unlike more melodramatic portrayals of Dalit suffering, *Court* uses a realistic, observational style to expose the absurdity and biases of state institutions, emphasizing how oppression can operate subtly yet pervasively.

In *Court*, Kamble's trial exposes how India's legal system becomes a site for the silent operation of caste hierarchies in front of the blindfolded *Kanoon* that itself is justice. The film can be read as a meditation on social currency that individuals from marginalized communities often lack. While the Constitution promises equality before the law, Kamble's lack of social power ensures that the law is wielded against him rather than for him. Foucault uses two terms namely, *nomos* which means law or custom, and *nomisma* which means currency. He writes that "The principle of altering the nomisma is also that of changing the custom, breaking with it, breaking up the rules, habits, conventions, and laws" (Foucault 242). Social currency cannot be changed without changing the law and customs of society, if we rephrase what Foucault implies while talking of the 'Cynic character' in society. Kamble's art and defiance challenge the very *social currency* that the courtroom sadly ends up preserving. His trial becomes less about legal guilt and more about disciplining and punishing a person who dares to rupture caste-bound (socially qualified) norms. In *Court*, Narayan Kamble lives the Cynic's *ale-the bios*, i.e., a life of openness with nothing to hide. In Foucault's conceptualization, oppressed people have to sometimes live a Cynic's life: "the life in ale-theia...a life without concealment,

which holds nothing back, a life which was capable of having nothing to be ashamed of” (243). Yet the court, as depicted in the film, cloaked in custom and procedure, conceals its own biases and punishes a man-without-institutional-power for embodying his very truth.

Geeli Puchhi

Geeli Puchhi (2021), a film segment from the anthology *Ajeeb Daastaans* (2021) directed by Neeraj Ghaywan, explores caste discrimination in a modern urban workplace through the evolving friendship between Priya Sharma, a Brahmin woman, and Bharti Mandal, her Dalit colleague. The central issue is how caste operates subtly in contemporary, ostensibly liberal spaces, through microaggressions, covert exclusion, and social hierarchies that go unnoticed but shape everyday interactions. Unlike rural-focused depictions in *Article 15* and *Fandry*, *Geeli Puchhi* shows that caste prejudice persists even in urban, modern contexts, challenging assumptions that urbanization and progress have lowered caste discrimination. The film segment emphasizes how Dalit agency navigates hidden hierarchies, revealing the quiet persistence of caste in shaping relationships, opportunities, and personal dignity. Let us try and understand this brief conversation between the two women characters in the film –

Bharti: So is that how you got the job?...

Priya: ...the manager asked me what my hobbies were. I told him I do palm-reading. That’s it. You learn that much in a Brahmin house. I looked at his palm...and I got a call the next day.

Bharti: They didn't ask you if you can work on Excel and Tally?

Priya: No. Sir said that Mr. Alok will teach me everything. Everyone's so helpful here.

(*Geeli Pucchi*, Subtitles)

In this brief yet telling exchange from the film, Priya's remark, "You learn that much in a Brahmin house" encapsulates how caste often masquerades as something innocent, inevitable, and cultural, while silently functioning as a credential in itself. What is framed as a *hobby* (palm reading, astrology etc) becomes a social capital that signals upper-caste identity and ensures access, even in a corporate space ostensibly governed by merit. The manager's reassurance that "Mr. Alok will teach [her] everything" reflects what sociologist Pierre Bourdieu calls *habitus* – the unearned ease and presumed potential attached to privileged caste loci. Priya's caste background is read as an assurance of trainability and intellect, while Bharti, a Dalit woman who has repeatedly demonstrated competence, is continually confronted with the discourse of 'merit' as a barrier to promotions. This very dynamic, which Sumeet Samos incisively critiques in his protest rap when he raps, "We build your houses, we till your lands...don't teach us merit, you good-for-nothing clans" (*Caste 101*), exposes the hypocrisy of a system that equates caste privilege with potential and Dalit labour with deficiency. In such modern workplace economies, caste does not disappear, but rather quietly hides itself under the garb of qualification.

There is another set of dialogue delivery between the two women, but this time with a twist inspired by silent revenge. The context is that despite trying to lay bare her truth entailing her

caste, in front of Priya, Bharti only receives silent altered responses from Priya. Yogesh Maitreya talks at length on how caste is a silent negotiation in elite spaces, reflective of this scene where Mondal reveals to her friend and colleague about her real caste. But, rather than reacting aggressively to her pain and disappointment and feeling the untold but clear rejection from the upper caste woman after the revelation, Mondal leads to a twisted turn of events in the film. She somehow convinces Priya to try having a baby with the husband she cannot be in love with. Priya trusts Bharati and seeks her suggestions on how to conceive –

Priya: Wao. You know so much. How did you learn?

Bharti: The same way you learnt palm-reading.

And finally, with her expert advice as she had planned, Bharti makes Priya quit her job for child bearing and postpartum responsibilities. It must be noted that Bharti, who is able to finish the same task in twenty minutes that Priya usually takes two hours to complete, must endure a path fraught with contempt, with her only form of resistance being manipulation. Let us consider another set of dialogues from the film.

Bharti: So I can't get the data operator job?

Factory Manager: It's time for my morning prayer. We'll talk about this later. Now get out...

(sometime later, at lunch)

Bharti: How long does it take to learn Excel and Tally?
Three days? Four Days? A week at most?

Aged male colleague: Even if you learn all that, you won't get the job.

Bharti: What do you mean? Why can't I get the job?...I have a degree, too, you know.

Aged male colleague: Because you're Bharti Mandal. Do you have a privileged-caste surname like Banerjee or Sharma? We are Dalits. Did you forget that for a moment?

(*Ajeeb Daastans*, subtitles)

Bharti is compelled to manipulate Priya precisely because the *nomos* (to use Foucault's term) is constructed to secure upper-caste women while marginalizing lower-caste women. Priya is granted sympathy and protection because the established *nomos* of Brahmanical patriarchy reserves these for women who fulfill the role of the secluded, pure subject. Conversely, Bharti is subjected to suspicion and scrutiny because the same *nomos* views her as a subject available for socio-sexual exploitation, only reducing her skills and labor into impurity and unreliability. Given these discriminatory circumstances, Bharti has no recourse but to play smarter to survive in a cruel world.

Conclusion

Across these five films, contemporary Indian cinema presents an evolving, though uneven, representation of Dalit experiences. In *Aarakshan*, Dalits like Deepak Kumar navigate structural barriers to education, highlighting both the promise and limitations of affirmative action while showing how upper-caste authority shapes opportunity and aspiration. *Article 15* shifts the lens to systemic violence, exposing institutional complicity and upper-caste

audiences' discovery of caste atrocities, though at the cost of detailed Dalit characterisation. *Fandry* brings the focus to everyday oppression and the emotional and aspirational costs of caste, showing how even personal desires, such as love, are circumscribed by social hierarchies; Jabya's final act of defiance symbolizes the psychological and social impulse to resist long-term subjugation. While *Court* is a demonstration of the life of a resisting Dalit man juxtaposed to the country's legal failure to provide him with any resolution, *Geeli Pucchi* brings a fresh and raw perspective on how caste functions silently in everyday life of Dalits in urban workspaces and relationships. Together, these films reveal a significant progression in the portrayal of Dalit characters, although their representation is still largely mediated through institutional and upper-caste perspectives.

The key finding is that cinema is beginning to grapple with caste both as a structural and interpersonal force, highlighting the complexity of Dalit life while also reflecting the persistent challenges of authentic and nuanced portrayal. The analytical engagement across the five discussed films employed a critical, intersectional framework to map the mechanisms of power and resistance concerning caste and gender in contemporary Indian society. The central finding establishes that institutional structures are still fundamentally governed by a logic of Brahmanical patriarchy and graded inequality, compelling subaltern subjects to adopt strategic forms of counter-conduct to attain justice.

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